

Interoperability

Metadata & Ontologies

Agricultural Sciences

INRAE

Leveraging AgroPortal ontologies to ease metadata completion and data discovery in Data INRAE

Overview

In recent years, a growing number of data repositories have been implemented to meet the need for publishing and reusing research data. In **the case of INRAE, research data is shared via domain repositories or via an institutional repository: Data INRAE**, now part of the French national federated research data platform Recherche Data Gouv.

This national repository is based on the open source research data repository software Dataverse. Data repository software allows datasets to be documented via metadata, but these often function as single texts rather than semantic concepts, without enrichment, extended search on related terms or multilingualism.

Semantic artifacts of interest to INRAE are hosted in AgroPortal, a repository for ontologies and other semantic artifacts in agri-food and related domains. This is based on the generic OntoPortal technology jointly developed by INRAE-MISTEA, the University of Montpellier and the OntoPortal Alliance. AgroPortal allows users to search and browse terms in an intuitive interface and can also be called automatically by tools via API. This use case aims to bridge the gap between these platforms; data repository and semantic artifact catalog, developing a connector in Data INRAE to be able to use the semantic artifacts of AgroPortal in an intuitive way and make them usable and available to all users of Dataverse or OntoPortal technologies.

Connector between Data INRAE and AgroPortal

Concretely, with this new feature:

- The dataverse manager selects relevant semantic artefacts from AgroPortal
- The data depositor picks keywords from ontologies and thesauri that have been connected
- Dataverse records URIs and any relevant information for these keywords
- Information from the selected keywords can be exported with other metadata of a dataset

This integration should make it possible to propose relevant semantic artifacts to the community with terms from agri-food vocabularies available on AgroPortal (and potentially in many other semantic artifact catalogs).

#user-friendliness - the work of describing and searching datasets should be simplified, while remaining intuitive and fast. Users will be involved in the specification and testing of new features.

#multilingualism - Data INRAE users generally work in English or French and AgroPortal semantic artifacts can be multilingual. Evolutions of the AgroPortal API are considered in connection with T4.2.

#modularity - In the case of multidisciplinary data repositories such as the Recherche Data Gouv repository, depositors from different communities may need to select concepts from specific vocabularies. To meet this need, the set of vocabularies to be used must be configurable at the level of dataverse collections.

#sustainability - A key challenge in this use case is to connect Data INRAE and AgroPortal, making this connection generic and reusable for other OntoPortal and Dataverse installations. The export functionality needs to be modified to include the URIs of the controlled terms used for indexing. The evolutions made are discussed and shared with both developer communities.

#evaluation - the use case needs to allow evaluating the impact of the proposed evolutions on the FAIRness of the data, especially on Findability.

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Expected impact of the Use Case

The outputs of the use cases will improve the FAIRness of INRAE datasets (agri-food research and technical data). The connection with the vocabulary repository (AgroPortal) will result in more and richer keywords added by data producers. The use of semantic artefacts will enable multilingual and synonymous search for greater discoverability and accessibility of datasets. **The use of documented, identified, unambiguous and more domain-relevant keywords thanks to external and specific semantic artefact systems**, which will allow greater interoperability of datasets. This will also promote and simplify the use of standard terms and semantic artefacts for communities.

These benefits will be achieved, while providing faster and easier metadata completion, thanks to the simplification of metadata fields and their filling.

Furthermore, **this should lead to increased use of semantic artefacts in platforms using this connector**. For example, AgroPortal will benefit from the needs of Agricultural Science users for additional or improved terms from Data INRAE. Other scientific domains that wish to benefit from such features should also produce new terms and artifacts in the semantic artifact catalogs. As these developments will be compatible not only with Data INRAE and AgroPortal installations but also with the software they use (Dataverse and Ontoport respectively). The functionality and its benefits will be reusable across all installations of these software in various domains.

Expected outputs

The tangible outcomes of this use case are:

- **Dataverse-OntoPortal connector** publically available in [the community's repository](#)
- **Global improvement of semantic artefacts use in Dataverse**
- **Analysis of current practices and impact** of the evolution on users and on datasets findability
- **Guidelines** on criteria to select relevant semantic artefacts for a data repository

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